

Experimental

Preparation of 2-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-1,3,5-triazine : 2,4,6-Trichloro-1,3,5-triazine (0.01 mole) and ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate (0.01 mole) were separately dissolved in acetone (100 ml) and mixed at 0°. To it, NaOH (aqueous 4%; 100 ml) was added dropwise and mechanically stirred at 0-5°. The contents poured on ice, titrated with HCl (5 N), filtered and crystallised from THF, m.p. 284° (reported m.p. 282-87°). (Found : C, 50.40 ; Cl, 24.8 ; N, 19.25. C₁₂H₁₀Cl₂N₄O₂ requires C, 51.25 ; Cl, 25.27 ; N, 19.97%).

Preparation of 2-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-4-chloro-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine : Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH, 0.08 mole) and 2-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-4,6-dichloro-1,3,5-triazine (0.08 mole) were dissolved in dioxane at 10 to 15°, followed by dropwise addition of NaHCO₃ (1 M; 90 ml) and stirring at 30-35° for 3 hr. The product isolated and crystallised from ethanol (95%), m.p. 325°. (Found : C, 56.22 ; H, 3.91 ; N, 24.38. C₁₈H₁₆ClN₇O₃ requires C, 55.89 ; H, 4.14 ; N, 25.36%).

Preparation of 2-arylamino-4-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine : Amine (0.032 mole) and 2-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-4-chloro-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine were taken in dioxane and the solution refluxed for 2 hr with the simultaneous dropwise addition of aqueous NaHCO₃ (10% ; 2 ml). The solution was cooled, poured on ice, filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (95%) in 80 to 85% yields.

Antimycobacterial screening : The *in vitro* anti-tubercular activity of the hitherto synthesised 2-arylamino-4-(4-carbethoxyanilino)-6-isonicotinylhydrazino-1,3,5-triazine have been studied at 25 µg/ml concentration (solvent-acetone) against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* using Lowenstein-Jensen medium. The procedure was duplicated with solvent for control purposes.

TABLE I—DATA OF THE 2-ARYLAMINO-4-(4-CARBETHOXYANILINO)-6-ISONICOTINYLHYDRAZINO-1,3,5-TRIAZINE

Sl. No.	Ar	m.p. °C	Activity against H ₃₇ R _v strain of <i>M. tuberculosis</i>
1.	Phenyl	150	+
2.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	218	+
3.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	231	+
4.	<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenyl	223	+
5.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	204	+
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	231	+
7.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	246	+
8.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	165	+
9.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	180	+
10.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	171	+
11.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	190	+
12.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	223	+

All the above compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

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Synthesis of Some New 1-Substituted 5-bromo-3-aryloxy acetyl hydrazono-2-indolinones as Potential Antibacterial Agents

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SEVERAL isatin analogues have been reported to possess antibacterial¹, antiviral², anthelmintic³, herbicidal⁴ and fungicidal⁵ properties. In addition to this, cysticidal⁶ and hypotensive⁷ responses have also been reported in certain isatin derivatives. Furthermore, tuberculostatic responses⁸ of aryloxy acetyl hydrazides are also well established.

Encouraged by these findings, 5-bromoisatin was condensed with *p*-substituted phenoxy acetyl hydrazides to furnish 5-bromo-3-aryloxy acetyl hydrazono-2-indolinones (I). Similarly, 5-bromo-1-methyl isatin gave 1-methyl-5-bromo-3-(*p*-substituted)-phenoxy acetyl hydrazono-2-indolinones. When compounds (I) were subjected to Mannich reaction, 1-aminomethyl-5-bromo-3-(*p*-substituted)-phenoxy acetyl hydrazono-2-indolinones were obtained and their antibacterial activity were tested.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. All the compounds were characterised by ir spectroscopy, recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137 IR spectrometer in KBr and the λ_{max} values are expressed in cm⁻¹. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel-G plates and the spots were located by I₂ vapours.

Synthesis of 5-bromoisatin (I) : The 5-bromoisatin was prepared following the literature method^{9,10}.

***N*-Methylation of isatin (II) :** This was performed by the procedure described by Harley-Manson *et al*¹¹.

Aryloxy acetyl hydrazides (III-VII): Hydrazone derivatives of substituted phenols were prepared by the method of Yale *et al.*².

3-Phenoxy acetyl hydrazono-2-indolinone (VIII): A mixture of 5-bromoisatin (4.4 g; 0.02 mole) and phenoxy acetyl hydrazide (3.3 g; 0.02 mole) in ethanol (25 ml) containing a few drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool to room temperature. The solid mass thus separated was filtered off, washed with cold ethanol and recrystallised from ethyl acetate.

IR: 3200 (N-H stretch, broad peak with shoulder), 1720 (C=O stretch shoulder at 1680 for non-cyclic C=O stretch) and 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N), etc.

All the other compounds of the series (IX-XII) were synthesised in a similar manner and their relevant data are given in Table 1.

1-Methyl-5-bromo-3-phenoxy acetyl hydrazono-2-indolinone (XIII): This was prepared by heating a mixture of 1-methyl-5-bromo isatin (1.2 g; 0.1 mole) and phenoxy acetyl hydrazide (0.83 g; 0.1 mole) in ethanol (25 ml) containing a few drops of glacial acetic acid for 4 hr on a water bath. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid product thus separated was recrystallised from CHCl_3 .

IR: 3150 (N-H stretch), 2900 (C-H stretch aliphatic), 1720 (C=O stretch cyclic), 1675 (C=O stretch non-cyclic) and 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N), etc.

Other compounds of this series (XIV-XVII) were also synthesised by the similar method (Table 1).

1-Morpholinomethyl-5-bromo-3-phenoxyacetyl hydrazono-2-indolinone (XVIII): The compound 5-bromo-3-phenoxy acetyl hydrazono-2-indolinone (1.24 g; 0.01 mole) was suspended in ethanol (15 ml). To this suspension was added 37% formalin (0.1 ml) and morpholine (0.2 ml; 0.01 mole) with vigorous stirring. This mixture was then heated on water bath for 10 min and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The separated product was filtered and washed with petroleum ether (60-80°) and air dried. Finally, it was recrystallised from CHCl_3 -petroleum ether.

IR: 3200 (N-H stretch), 2850 (C-H stretch aliphatic), 1720 (C=O stretch cyclic), 1675 (C=O stretch non-cyclic), and 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N), etc.

Similarly, compounds (XIX-XXVII) were also synthesised (Table 1).

Antibacterial activity: The method of agar diffusion technique^{13,14} was employed for determining antibacterial activity of all the compounds. The test organisms included *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus pumilus*. Sterile filter paper discs (diameter 5 mm) saturated with the solution of the test compound (10 mg/ml in ethanol) were placed on nutrient agar plates [1.5% (w/v) agar, 5% (w/v) NaCl, 0.5% (w/v) glucose and 3.5% (w/v) peptone; pH 6.8-7.0], after drying up of the solvent. The plates were incubated at 37° for

24 hr. Inhibition zones around the discs were measured. Tests were carried out in triplicate and the results are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF 1-SUBSTITUTED-5-BROMO-3-ARYLOXY ACETYL HYDRAZONO-2-INDOLINONES (VIII-XXVII)

Compd. No.	R	R'	m.p. °C	Antibacterial activity		
				Mean inhibition area after 24 hr	<i>B. cereus</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
VIII	H	H	230	++	++	++
IX	H	Cl	242	++	+	-
X	H	CH_3	272	+	+	+
XI	H	OCH_3	238	+	-	+
XII	H	Br	252	-	+	-
XIII	CH_3	H	212	-	+	+
XIV	CH_3	Cl	202	+	-	+
XV	CH_3	OCH_3	218	-	-	-
XVI	CH_3	OCH_3	183	-	-	-
XVII	CH_3	Br	192	-	-	-
XVIII	morpholino methyl	H	152	+++	++	++
XIX	"	Cl	139	+	+	+
XX	"	CH_3	146	+	-	+
XXI	"	OCH_3	147	+	-	+
XXII	"	Br	178	-	+	-
XXIII	piperidino methyl	H	158	+	-	+
XXIV	"	Cl	176	-	+	+
XXV	"	CH_3	184	+	+	+
XXVI	"	OCH_3	155	+	-	-
XXVII	"	Br	164	-	-	-

Elemental analysis of C, H and N were found within limits. Yields of all the compounds ranged between 60-80%.

(-) = No inhibition, (+) = Zone size 6-8 mm, (++) = Zone size 8-12 mm, (+++) = Zone size > 12 mm.

Discussion

Compounds no 8 and 18 were found to be the most active against all the microorganisms tested, whereas compound no. 9 was found to be active only against *B. cereus*. Rest of the compounds were moderately active.

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Synthesis of Substituted 6-Pyrazolo and 6-Isoxazolo-Benzoxazoles and Their Physiological Activity

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A wide range of physiological properties are found to be associated with benzoxazoles, isoxazoles and pyrazoles. Heterocycles, substituted with hydroxyphenyl moiety, have been used as analgesic¹, antitissuive² and anticonvulsant³ agents. A number of hydroxyaryl pyrazoles were found to possess marked antifungal activity⁴. The present investigation is aimed at a study of antifungal activity of some substituted isoxazolobenzoxazoles and pyrazolobenzoxazoles and a series of the above new compounds are synthesised and screened for antifungal and antibacterial activities.

Chromones in their reactions with hydrazine or phenylhydrazine behave like α,β -unsaturated ketones

and undergo Michael addition. The nucleophile attacks at C-2 with concomitant opening of the pyrone ring. The intermediates thus formed undergo cyclisation to give 3(5)-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-pyrazole system^{5,6}.

Chart 1. R=alkyl or aryl; R'=H or ph

In the present investigation, the behaviour of some substituted chromonooxazoles with hydroxylamine, hydrazine and phenylhydrazine is studied. Substituted chromonooxazoles can be prepared starting from *o*-hydroxyaminochromones either by treating with various aldehydes in nitrobenzene⁷ or treatment with carboxylic acids in presence of polyphosphoric acid⁸.

Chromonooxazoles (I), upon treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine, underwent the cleavage of the chromone ring followed by the formation of isoxazole unit, resulting in the formation of II. The same chromonooxazole (I), when treated with hydrazinehydrate or phenylhydrazine in alcohol medium yielded III (Chart 2). These results are in accordance with Ghosh *et al.*⁹.

Chart 2

All the products gave green colouration with neutral ferric chloride, pink colour with conc. sulphuric acid and dark violet colour with titanium(III) chloride. The uv maxima are recorded at 250 ± 10 nm due to benzoxazole chromophore and at 280 ± 10 nm due to extended conjugation. The ir bands at 1570, 1350, 1050 cm^{-1} are characteristic of oxazole ring system. A broad absorption at 3200 cm^{-1} is for chelated hydroxyl group. Further, absorption at 1640 cm^{-1} is indicative of >C=N . The pmr results have been included in Table 1.

Physiological activity :

All the above compounds have been tested for antibacterial activity using *Staphylococcus lutea*,